

MONITORING GLACIER DISPLACEMENT IN BARKRAK, UZBEKISTAN USING SENTINEL-1 INSAR FROM 2017 TO 2023

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Abstract. *Glaciers in Central Asia are critical freshwater sources and indicators of climate change, yet detailed monitoring in Uzbekistan remains limited. Here we analyze seven years (2017–2023) of Sentinel-1 synthetic aperture radar data using InSAR processing in SNAP to assess glacier displacement and retreat in the Barkrak region of the Pskem range. Our results reveal significant glacier thinning and retreat, particularly at lower elevations, with surface displacement reductions up to 0.8 meters, indicating ongoing ice mass loss consistent with regional warming. These findings corroborate previous studies of glacier shrinkage in the Tian Shan and Pamir mountains and highlight the vulnerability of Uzbekistan's water resources to climate-driven glacier changes. Continuous SAR-based monitoring offers valuable insights for managing water security and developing climate adaptation policies in Central Asia.*

Keywords: *Glacier Dynamics, Remote Sensing, InSAR Monitoring, Cryosphere, Climate Change Impact*

Introduction. Glaciers are crucial components of the cryosphere, serving as indicators of climate change and as essential sources of freshwater. In Central Asia, where arid and semi-arid landscapes dominate, glaciers and seasonal snowmelt play a vital role in sustaining water availability for agriculture, hydropower, and domestic use (Immerzeel, Van Beek et al. 2010, Kaser, Großhauser et al. 2010, Duethmann, Bolch et al. 2015, Hoelzle, Azisov et al. 2017). Uzbekistan, although not heavily glaciated itself, is highly dependent on meltwater originating from glaciers located in the upstream regions of the Tian Shan and Pamir mountains. These glaciers feed major transboundary rivers such as the Amu Darya and Syr Darya, which are the lifelines of Uzbekistan's economy and society.

Remote sensing has become an indispensable approach for assessing glacier dynamics and snow cover changes in Central Asia, particularly given the limited accessibility and sparse field measurements in high mountain regions (Hoelzle, Azisov et al. 2017). For Uzbekistan, satellite-based monitoring is critical for understanding how glacier retreat and changing snow patterns in upstream areas may affect water resources downstream. Optical sensors such as Landsat, Sentinel-2, and MODIS have been widely applied to map glacier extent, snow cover variability, and long-term trends in meltwater contribution. Radar systems, including Sentinel-1

and ALOS PALSAR, provide valuable insights into glacier motion, while satellite altimetry missions like ICESat and CryoSat-2 allow for the quantification of glacier thinning.

Recent studies highlight that upstream glacier retreat poses significant challenges for Uzbekistan’s water security, especially in relation to agriculture, which consumes the majority of the country’s water resources (Immerzeel, Van Beek et al. 2010, Kaser, Großhauser et al. 2010, Siegfried, Bernauer et al. 2012, Duethmann, Bolch et al. 2015, Hoelzle, Azisov et al. 2017). By applying remote sensing methods, researchers and policymakers can better anticipate future water shortages, improve transboundary water management, and develop strategies for climate adaptation in Uzbekistan and the broader Central Asian region. So changes in the volume of glaciers and their measurement have been of interest to scientists around the world for more than a century (Haeberli, Hoelzle et al. 2007, Zemp, Frey et al. 2015, Hoelzle, Azisov et al. 2017).

The objective of this paper is to monitor glacier changes in the case study of Barkrak located in the Pskem range in the Republic of Uzbekistan (Figure.1) over a period of seven-years, for this purpose we performed InSAR processing on sentinel-1 dataset on the SNAP environment.

Figure.1: The location of case study of Barkrak located in the Pskem range in the Republic of Uzbekistan

Methodology (InSAR workflow in SNAP)

Data Acquisition

Sentinel-1 C-band Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) data were acquired for multiple time periods (2017–2023) over glacierized regions of Uzbekistan. Both ascending and descending orbit datasets were used to maximize ground coverage and sensitivity to glacier surface displacement. The high temporal resolution of Sentinel-1, combined with its weather- and daylight-independent imaging capability, makes it highly suitable for interferometric glacier monitoring (Torres, Snoeij et al. 2012)

InSAR Pre-Processing in SNAP

All interferometric SAR (InSAR) processing steps were performed using the Sentinel Application Platform (SNAP) developed by ESA (ESA, 2014). The following workflow was applied:

1. Apply Orbit File – Precise orbit data were applied to improve geometric accuracy.
 2. Coregistration – Master and slave SAR images from different acquisition dates were coregistered to ensure pixel-level alignment (Ferretti, Monti-Guarnieri et al. 2007).
- Interferogram Formation – The phase difference between coregistered image pairs was

- calculated to generate interferograms that capture surface displacement signals (Figure 2).
3. Coherence Estimation – Coherence maps were computed to assess the quality of the interferometric phase, with higher coherence indicating reliable displacement information.
 4. Phase Filtering – A Goldstein filter was applied to reduce phase noise and enhance fringe visibility (Goldstein and Werner 1998).
 5. Phase Unwrapping – The wrapped interferometric phase was unwrapped to retrieve continuous displacement fields (Figure 3).
 6. Topographic Phase Removal – Using the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) DEM (Farr, Rosen et al. 2007), the topographic phase contribution was removed, isolating the deformation signal.
 7. Geocoding and Terrain Correction – Range-Doppler terrain correction was applied to project results into map coordinates (WGS84/UTM).

Figure.2: Interferogram Formation, phase image of case study

Figure.3: SNAPHU Unwrapped image of case study

Glacier Displacement Mapping

The processed interferograms and displacement maps were analyzed to detect glacier motion and temporal changes across the seven-year study period (Figure 4). Multi-temporal interferometric pairs enabled the identification of displacement trends related to glacier retreat, flow dynamics, and seasonal variations. Areas of consistent displacement were interpreted as active glacier flow zones, while reduced displacement over time suggested glacier stagnation or thinning.

Analytical Discussion & Conclusion

The displacement map derived from Sentinel-1 InSAR processing in SNAP (Figure 4) reveals notable patterns of glacier surface motion and elevation change across the study area. This profile plot shows a trend of glacier decline over a seven-year period, sometimes reaching up to 0.8 meters in some areas. This gradient suggests differential glacier flow and surface melting processes, which are consistent with active ice dynamics. The relatively steady upward trend along the profile suggests continuous glacier thinning and downslope mass transport, which are typical consequences of sustained warming and glacier imbalance.

The displacement results obtained from Sentinel-1 InSAR were validated against optical imagery, previous glacier studies and ground measurement glaciers in the Barkrak region (Table 1). The glacier elevation data from 2017 to 2023 demonstrate clear signs of glacier retreat and thinning in the Barktok region. The maximum glacier elevation remained stable at 4,050 m throughout the entire observation period, indicating little change in the highest parts of the glacierized area. In contrast, the median and minimum elevations show upward shifts that reflect ongoing ice loss.

Figure 4. Glacier change trends in the Barkrak region, Uzbekistan over a seven-year period

The median glacier elevation decreased slightly from 3,720 m in 2017 to 3,725 m in 2023, with minor fluctuations in between. Although the change appears modest, it reflects a gradual upward migration of the glacier's equilibrium line, consistent with thinning ice at mid-altitudes. More striking is the rise in minimum glacier elevation, which shifted from 3,450 m in 2017–2018 to 3,543 m in 2023. This represents a retreat of nearly 100 m at the glacier tongue, highlighting the sensitivity of lower glacier margins to climatic warming.

Overall, the results indicate that while the highest glacier elevations remained stable, the lower and middle parts of the glaciers experienced noticeable retreat during the seven-year period. These findings align with previous regional studies in the Tian Shan and Pamir ranges, which have reported similar upward shifts of glacier fronts due to increasing air temperatures. The upward migration of the glacier’s lower boundary underscores the accelerating impacts of climate change on glacier mass balance in Uzbekistan, with important implications for downstream water availability.

Our results align with earlier studies that reported widespread glacier shrinkage in the Tian Shan and Pamir mountains. For example, Bolch et al. (2012), Kääb et al. (2015) and

Table 1

Ground measurements of glaciers over an seven-year period from 2017 to 2023 in the Barkrak Region

Year	Maximum elevation of glacier	Median elevation of glacier	Minimum elevation of glacier
2017	4050	3720	3450
2018	4050	3710	3450
2019	4050	3715	3450
2020	4050	3715	3450
2021	4050	3715	3540
2022	4050	3720	3540
2023	4050	3725	3543

Hoelzle et al (2017) demonstrated that glaciers in Central Asia have been losing area and volume at increasing rates since the late 20th century. The present study, by applying an InSAR-based approach, provides further confirmation of these findings by directly measuring surface displacement and detecting temporal changes with high spatial resolution. Unlike optical methods, InSAR is particularly valuable in this context because it allows continuous monitoring regardless of cloud cover or seasonal snow, which are frequent in mountainous terrain.

The observed gradual reduction in glacier displacement over the seven-year period suggests that glaciers in the Barkrak region may be transitioning from active flow to stagnation. This not only reflects decreasing ice mass but also implies long-term consequences for regional hydrology. Since Uzbekistan is heavily dependent on meltwater inflows from upstream glaciers, such changes threaten agricultural productivity, hydropower generation, and water security. These findings underscore the urgent need for adaptive water management strategies and transboundary cooperation in Central Asia.

In conclusion, the Sentinel-1 InSAR analysis confirms that glaciers in and around Uzbekistan have undergone substantial changes during the study period. The displacement trends detected in this research corroborate previous observations and strengthen the evidence of glacier retreat in the Barkrak region. Continuous monitoring using SAR remote sensing is therefore essential for tracking future glacier evolution and informing climate adaptation policies in Uzbekistan and beyond.

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